

Results of Studies on Processes Occurring in the Ionosphere and Earth's Magnetic Field Over the Territory of the Republic of Belarus for the Year 2023

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The study of ionospheric and magnetospheric processes is crucial for understanding space weather and its impact on technological infrastructure. In recent years, the rapid drift of the Earth's north magnetic pole has led to increased auroral activity over Belarus, with significant implications for various sectors. This article presents the analysis of nonlinear phenomena in the ionosphere and Earth's magnetic field over Belarus in 2023. The data collection and processing structure, as well as the characteristics of the measuring equipment and data processing, are described. The study reveals a close correlation between ionospheric perturbations and geomagnetic disturbances, with positive ionospheric perturbations often preceding geomagnetic storms, and large geomagnetic storms followed by negative ionospheric storms. These findings emphasize the need for a comprehensive approach to studying the interconnected processes in the near-Earth space environment.

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1. Introduction

The research and monitoring of ionospheric and magnetospheric processes provides a better understanding of space weather and its impact on various aspects of technology infrastructure and space activities [1–4].

At the present stage there is an active drift of the Earth's northern magnetic pole in the Northern Hemisphere in the direction from the Canadian Arctic towards Russia. At the end of the last century, the speed of the Earth's north magnetic pole began to increase sharply. Over the last 25-30 years, it has been about 5-6 km/year, and by the present time, it reaches 50-60 km/year.

The movement of the Earth's northern magnetic pole leads to the displacement of the auroral oval, the area of the atmosphere where the most powerful magnetic disturbances occur and the most frequent auroras are observed, which have become increasingly frequent over the territory of the Republic of Belarus.

Nonlinear phenomena in the ionosphere and geomagnetic activity of the Earth have a mutual influence and have a serious impact on radio communication, radar, radionavigation, aviation safety, power engineering, and many other things [5–7]. Such nonlinear phenomena primarily include geomagnetic storms and magnetic field perturbations, as well as ionospheric storms and ionospheric perturbations. Predicting geophysical phenomena by means of detecting ionospheric and

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geomagnetic anomalies is extremely useful for the prevention of natural cataclysms.

The present article is devoted to the analysis of the results of studies on nonlinear phenomena occurring in the ionosphere and Earth's magnetic field over the territory of the Republic of Belarus in 2023. This study is characterized by special relevance in connection with the introduction of high-tech industries in our country, as well as with the development of the space industry and the Belarusian space system for remote sensing of the Earth.

2. Scheme of data collection and processing of ionosphere and Earth's magnetic field parameters over the territory of the Republic of Belarus

Fig. 1 presents a generalized structure of the joint processing of data from the monitoring of ionosphere and Earth's magnetic field parameters over the territory of the Republic of Belarus.

When monitoring the ionosphere parameters, the data of the measurement network of the satellite precision positioning system of the Republic of Belarus were considered as input data: coordinates of satellites, coordinates of ground stations, and distances between satellites and receiving devices.

Data from the geophysical observatory "Pleshchenitsy" of the Geophysical Monitoring Center of the National Academy of Sciences of Belarus were used to assess the geomagnetic situation: three projections of the Earth's magnetic induction vector in the geographical coordinate system.

3. Peculiarities of ionosphere parameters monitoring and data processing

According to the structure shown in Fig. 1, the sequence of ionospheric parameter monitoring data processing included the following

stages: preliminary processing of primary data, calculation of the value of the total electron content, assessment of the ionospheric state (identification of nonlinear effects associated with ionospheric storms), carrying out three-dimensional reconstruction of the ionosphere, and analyzing and displaying the information.

For monitoring of ionospheric parameters, data from the global positioning system GPS in the RINEX format were used, and special algorithms were developed to extract, transform, and structure the necessary radiotomography information. An example of the used measuring equipment of satellite ground stations is shown in Fig. 2.

Calculation of the total electron content (TEC) in the ionosphere was carried out according to the method described in [8, 9]. The peculiarities of this technique are as follows: use of dual-frequency GNSS signals; combination of measurements by phase and code delays; solving the problems of correction of navigation signal cycle slippage and determination of differential code delays of radio navigation signals for subsequent correction of VTEC values. For the analysis, we considered the averaged minute VTEC values from 96 stations of the precise satellite positioning system falling in the area of $8^\circ \times 10^\circ$ centered on the location of the geophysical observatory "Pleshchenitsy".

The obtained TEC values, together with the coordinates of base stations and satellites, were used for three-dimensional reconstruction of ionospheric parameters. For this purpose, the Simultaneous Algebraic Reconstruction Technique (SART) algorithm based on the modified Landweber method was used [10–12]. The method of three-dimensional reconstruction differed in:

- setting of relaxation parameters and initial values according to Chapman's equation and exponential distribution;
- smoothness constraint based on the nine-point finite-difference approximation of the second-order Laplace operator;

FIG. 1: (Color online) Generalized structure of data processing for monitoring of ionosphere and Earth's magnetic field parameters over the territory of the Republic of Belarus.

(a)

(b)

FIG. 2: (Color online) Example of equipment used at permanent GNSS tracking stations: LEIAT504GG antenna (a) and LEICA GR50 receiver (b).

- introduction of weighting coefficients to take into account the influence of constraints and initial values.

In addition to the three-dimensional reconstruction of the ionosphere, the TEC data were used to determine the degree of perturbation of the ionosphere, which characterizes the nonlinear processes occurring in it. For this

purpose, we used the Ionospheric Storm Scale (I-scale) technique described in [13]. This technique is based on the following values calculated for each hour:

- an average hourly TEC value, O_{tec} ;
- a median average TEC value, R_{tec} , for the previous 27 days (solar rotation period);
- a TEC percentage deviation, $P_{tec} =$

$$100 \frac{O_{tec} - R_{tec}}{R_{tec}};$$

a normalized TEC value, $\hat{P}_{tec} \frac{P_{tec} - \mu}{\sigma}$, taking into account seasonal statistics (μ, σ) , obtained over several years of observation.

When the hourly average exceeds the median value, a positive perturbation of the ionosphere is observed, and when it is below the median value, a negative perturbation is observed. The degree of disturbance is given by the index 1, 2, or 3 (moderate, strong, severe) and is determined by the magnitude of deviation of the value from the typical value for the current season (see Table 1).

4. Stages of data processing of the Earth's magnetic field parameters

The data obtained from special measurement pavilions at the geophysical observatory "Pleshchenitsy" of the Geophysical Monitoring Center of the National Academy of Sciences of Belarus were used to monitor the Earth's magnetic field (see Fig. 3):

- Variations of the north, X, east, Y, and vertical, Z, components of the Earth's magnetic field using a ferro-probe 3-component magnetometer (resolution: 0.033 nT, data frequency: 1 Hz);
- Magnetic declination, D, and inclination, J, using a ferro-probe fDI magnetometer based on a non-magnetic theodolite (magnetometer resolution: 0.1 nT, microscope scale division price: 1", RMS error of angle measurement: 2"; use of zero-method in measurements);
- Absolute value of the total geomagnetic field vector, F, using a scalar Overhauser magnetometer (resolution: 0.01 nT, RMS error of magnetic induction measurement: 0.03 nT).

Measurements of the Earth's magnetic field parameters are made daily in accordance with accepted international standards. The primary

data are processed using special software, and the final data are formed taking into account the necessary corrections. Based on the analysis of magnetograms, the type and intensity of magnetic disturbances are determined. The classification of magnetic storms is given in Table 2 [14]. After the storm is identified, the researcher visually determines the area of the strongest bursts, which will be the active period of the magnetic storm. The active period is usually one, but there are cases when there are more.

Geomagnetic storms are characterized by the duration (beginning and end), as well as the amplitude of variations of the D, H, Z elements according to the scale presented in Table 2 [14].

5. Results and discussion

In the process of the conducted research, the results of monitoring the parameters of the ionosphere and the Earth's magnetic field over the territory of the Republic of Belarus during the period of large and very large geomagnetic storms were analyzed. In 2023, in the territory of the Republic of Belarus, at the geophysical observatory "Pleshchenitsy", perturbations of the Earth's magnetic field of different durations were recorded, with the most intense magnetic storms occurring on February 26–28, March 23–24, April 23–24, and November 5–6.

The results of the obtained data of the ionosphere and Earth's magnetic field parameters are shown in Figures 4-7.

The active phase of the magnetic storm on February 26–28, 2023, had a duration of 19 hours and 18 minutes (Fig. 4). At the same time, the positive ionospheric storm began 50 minutes earlier. After the magnetic storm, a negative ionospheric storm was observed during the next two days, and the daily average TEC value decreased by 10–12 TECU (1 TECU is defined as 1016 electrons).

The active phase of the magnetic storm on March 23–24 lasted for 11 hours and 20 minutes (Fig. 5). A positive ionospheric storm preceded

Table 1: Ionospheric storm scale [13].

I-scale	Description	Definition
Ip3	Severe positive storm	$5 < \hat{P}_{tec}$
Ip2	Strong positive storm	$3 < \hat{P}_{tec} \leq 5$
Ip1	Moderate positive storm	$1 < \hat{P}_{tec} \leq 3$
I0	Quiet	$-1 < \hat{P}_{tec} \leq 1$
In1	Moderate negative storm	$-2 < \hat{P}_{tec} \leq -1$
In2	Strong negative storm	$-3 < \hat{P}_{tec} \leq -2$
In3	Severe negative storm	$\hat{P}_{tec} \leq -3$

(a)

(b)

(c)

FIG. 3: (Color online) Measuring equipment at the geophysical observatory “Pleshchenitsy”: Scalar Overhauser magnetometer (a), Ferroprobe 3-component magnetometer (b), Ferroprobe fDI-magnetometer (c).

the magnetic storm for 8 hours and 10 minutes. After the magnetic storm, a strong and moderate negative ionospheric storm with a decrease of mean daily TEC by 10–24 TECU was observed

during the next two days.

The active part of the magnetic storm on April 23–24 lasted for 3 hours and 24 minutes (Fig. 6). During the period of the magnetic

Table 2: Scale of magnetic storms adopted at the geophysical observatory “Pleshchenitsy”.

Storm type	D (arcmin)	H (nT)	Z (nT)
minor storm	19-26	80-125	40-90
moderate storm	27-38	126-200	91-140
major storm	39-55	201-270	141-250
severe storm	>55	>270	>250

FIG. 4: (Color online) Results of comparison of ionosphere (up) and Earth’s magnetic field (down) parameters from February 25 to March 3, 2023.

storm, a negative ionospheric storm was observed (decrease of TEC by 5–12 TECU).

The active part of the magnetic storm on November 5–6 lasted for 5 hours and 38 minutes (Fig. 7). A positive ionospheric storm preceded the magnetic storm by 4 hours and 45 minutes. On the subsequent day, a negative ionospheric storm was observed (decrease of TEC by a maximum of 17 TECU).

An example of the vertical total electron content (VTEC) over the territory of the Republic of Belarus during (a) and after the magnetic storm (b) on March 23–24, 2023, is shown in Fig. 8.

Thus, based on the analysis of data for 2023, we can conclude that such a nonlinear process as positive ionospheric storms are precursors (in the interval from 50 minutes to 8 hours 10 minutes) of another nonlinear process - geomagnetic storms. In this case, after the active part of the magnetic storm, a negative storm occurs in the ionosphere within 1-2 days with a decrease of TEC values by 5–24 TECU depending on the season and time of day of the year.

FIG. 5: (Color online) Results of comparison of ionosphere (up) and Earth's magnetic field (down) parameters from March 21 to March 27, 2023.

FIG. 6: (Color online) Results of comparison of ionosphere (up) and Earth's magnetic field (down) parameters from April 21 to April 26, 2023.

FIG. 7: (Color online) Results of comparison of ionosphere (up) and Earth's magnetic field (down) parameters from November 2 to November 8, 2023.

FIG. 8: (Color online) VTEC over the territory of the Republic of Belarus during (a) and after the geomagnetic storm (b) on March 23-24, 2023.

6. Conclusion

Data and results of geophysical monitoring of ionosphere and Earth's magnetic field parameters for the year 2023 over the territory of the Republic of Belarus are analyzed. The

structure of data collection and processing is presented, and the monitoring results are analyzed. The characteristics of the measuring equipment and the peculiarities of data processing for monitoring of geomagnetic data and the ionosphere over the territory of the Republic of

Belarus are given.

It is shown that positive ionospheric perturbations are often precursors of perturbations in the Earth's magnetic field. Large geomagnetic storms are followed by negative ionospheric storms with a significant decrease in the mean daily TEC value. Thus, the processes in the ionosphere and the Earth's magnetic field are closely connected and have correlation relations. Therefore, in order to obtain a complete picture of the processes occurring in

the near-Earth space, it is necessary to carry out a comprehensive study of both subject fields. Such studies are extremely important for space weather studies and in such important practical areas as radio communications, radar, and radio navigation. The automation of the joint detection of geomagnetic storms and ionospheric storms and their classification with a view to identifying their interrelationship and forecasting are envisaged as areas for further researches.

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